

ASSESSMENT OF CLINICAL, LABORATORY AND IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS AFTER ALLOPLASTY FOR VENTRAL HERNIAS

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of using lightweight and heavyweight polypropylene endoprosthesis for onlay hernioplasty. A comparison of the two types of polypropylene materials revealed that the lightweight polypropylene endoprosthesis used in the main group had better biocompatibility, which was expressed in a less pronounced exudative phase of inflammation and an earlier onset of the proliferation phase.*

Keywords: *postoperative ventral hernias, alloplasty, polypropylene mesh.*

Introduction. Abdominal hernias are among the most common surgical pathologies and occur in 4–7% of the adult population. Postoperative ventral hernias (POVH) develop in 5–12% of patients after laparotomy [1,4,6,10,13]. In cases of autoplasty using local tissues for hernia gate closure, the recurrence rate can reach 46–53% [5,9].

The main surgical treatment method for POVH is tension-free repair [10,11]. Currently, implants are produced that feature high strength, elasticity, biocompatibility, and favorable physical and mechanical properties [2,7,10,12].

It is known that all mesh endoprosthesis used in hernioplasty are classified as heavy, standard, or lightweight, depending on their structure and filament thickness [3,8,15].

Lightweight meshes are characterized by pronounced biocompatibility, due to the reduced amount of foreign material implanted into tissues, which in turn provides better tissue integration of the endoprosthesis [3,6,14].

Research objective. To study the outcomes of using lightweight and heavyweight polypropylene (PP) mesh based on clinical and laboratory parameters, as well as clinical research results in patients with postoperative ventral hernias (POVH).

Materials and Methods. A total of 137 patients were observed, who were divided into a comparison group (64 patients) and a main group (73 patients). In group I (comparison group), a heavyweight polypropylene endoprosthesis was implanted, while in group II (main group), a lightweight polypropylene endoprosthesis was used. All patients underwent abdominal wall defect repair using the onlay technique.

The characteristics of the groups are presented in Table 1. As seen from the table, the groups were statistically homogeneous in terms of patients' sex, age, types, and sizes of ventral hernias.

Results and Discussion. In 64 patients of the comparison group who received “heavyweight polypropylene,” the body temperature remained subfebrile for up to 6 days and normalized only by day 7.

At the first stage, we studied the body's temperature response to “heavyweight polypropylene” and “lightweight polypropylene” implants in a comparative aspect. The dynamics of the temperature response are presented in Figure 1.

In the study of the temperature response in 73 patients of the main group who received “lightweight polypropylene,” an elevated temperature was observed for up to 4 days (Figure 1), and it normalized by days 6–7.

Table 1.

Distribution of Patients by Sex and Age in the Groups

Patient Groups (n = 137)			Comparison Group (n = 64)		Main Group (n = 73)	
			abs.	%	abs.	%
Age (years)	under 20	M	-		-	
		F	-		-	
	20-39	M	1	1,6±1,6	1	1,4±1,4
		F	2	3,1±2,2	3	4,1±2,3
	40-59	M	3	4,7±2,7	5	6,8±3,0
		F	27	42,2±6,2	29	39,7±5,8
	60-74	M	5	7,8±3,4	6	8,2±3,2
		F	24	37,5±6,1	26	35,6±5,6
	75 and <	M	1	1,6±1,6	2	2,7±1,9
		F	1	1,6±1,6	1	1,4±1,4

However, in 5 patients of the main group whose drains were removed on days 3 to 5, a temperature increase from 37.5°C to 38.9°C was observed. The cause of the fever was seromas, which were evacuated, leading to normalization of the temperature.

Figure 1. Dynamics of the postoperative temperature response depending on the type of mesh used.

The temperature response in patients of the comparison group was significantly higher than in the main group at all time points of the study.

The dynamics of leukocyte levels ($\times 10^9/L$) in the postoperative period, depending on the type of mesh used, are presented in Figure 2. As shown in Figure 2, leukocyte elevation ranged from 8 to 10 thousand over 6 days in the comparison group and up to 5 days in the main group. Leukocytosis normalized by day 7 in the comparison group, and by day 6 in the main group. As seen in Figure 2, in both groups, the peripheral blood leukocyte levels were elevated starting from day 2, gradually decreasing by days 6–7.

In patients of the comparison group, leukocytosis—unlike in the main group—tended to gradually increase from the early postoperative period, followed by a slow decline toward the end of the observation period, reaching its peak on days 4 and 5: 12.4 ± 0.41 and 12.5 ± 0.42 ($\times 10^9/L$).

Figure 2. Dynamics of blood leukocyte levels ($\times 10^9/L$) in the comparison groups.

The study of postoperative wound exudates showed the following results. It was reliably established that hemorrhagic discharge in patients of the main group lasted for one day, while serous-hemorrhagic fluid was produced for up to 3 days. Serous discharge was observed on day 4 in 12 patients, all of whom had undergone surgery for postoperative ventral hernias. On days 4–5, serous discharge persisted in 2 patients of the main group. In 22 patients (34.3%) of the comparison group, the formation of paraprothetic masses in the area of the postoperative wound was observed during the early postoperative period.

Unlike the main group, patients in the comparison group exhibited prolonged wound exudate production, lasting up to 6 days. On postoperative day 3, the maximum volume of exudate was recorded at 61.4 ± 4.2 ml. A significant difference was observed in the dynamics of the exudative response between the comparison and main groups. In the comparison group, exudate production was high from the early postoperative period and gradually decreased over time. In the main group, a steady reduction was observed by days 3–4. In 12 patients of the main group, due to a decrease in wound drainage volume to 20 ml by day 4, the drains were removed following ultrasound evaluation.

The duration of drain placement was 4.1 ± 1.1 days in the main group and 6.1 ± 1.5 days in the comparison group.

Figure 3. Dynamics of wound exudate volume in the postoperative period depending on the type of mesh used

In the postoperative period, continuous active aspiration of wound secretions was performed through the drainage tubes placed in the wound cavity. The results of the cytological examination of wound exudate over time are presented in Table 2.

In smears of wound exudate from the paraprothetic space, both in the main group and the comparison group, the secretions on days 1–2 were hemorrhagic due to the presence of erythrocytes. The dynamics of the tissue response showed an increase in the number of mononuclear phagocytic system cells (i.e., cells that play an important role in infection defense) from days 3 to 4, along with a decrease in inflammatory cells. Indicators characterizing the inflammatory phase of the tissue response (such as the number of granulocytes and lymphocytes) indicate that in both the comparison and main groups, the peak of inflammation occurred on day 3 following endoprosthesis implantation. Starting from day 5, an increase in macrophages and fibroblasts was observed, which indicates the transition of the wound process to the reparative phase. It should be noted that in patients of the main group, on postoperative day 5, the inflammatory response (based on granulocyte count) was less pronounced, while the fibroplastic response (based on the content of macrophages and fibroblasts in the wound exudate) was more pronounced than in the comparison group ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.

Percentage content of main cellular elements in cytological examination of wound exudate

Cellular elements	Polypropylene – heavyweight (n = 64)			Polypropylene – lightweight (n = 73)		
	2nd day	Days 3–4	Days 5–7	2nd day	Days 3–4	Days 5–7
Granulocytes	55,0±1,8	43,0±1,5	39,0±1,3	53,0±1,7	40,0±1,4	35,0±1,2*
Lymphocytes	26,0±0,86	29,0±0,97	27,0±0,89	25,0±0,82	28,0±0,92	26,0±0,85
Macrophages	12,0±0,39	18,0±0,60	20,0±0,66	19,0±0,63***	19,0±0,64	23,0±0,76**
Fibroblasts	3,0±0,10	8,0±0,26	14,0±0,47	9,0±0,30***	9,0±0,29*	16,0±0,52*

Note: * – statistically significant compared to the values of the comparison group (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$)

Thus, based on the characteristics of the drainage exudate, it can be concluded that in the main group of patients, the transition from inflammatory-type exudate to regenerative-type exudate occurs earlier than in the comparison group.

When analyzing the characteristics of drainage exudate, we obtained the following results (Table 3). In the main group, the transition from inflammatory-type wound exudate to regenerative-type occurred two days earlier than in the comparison group. Therefore, the use of the lightweight polypropylene endoprosthesis, due to its structural features, is associated with a less pronounced inflammatory tissue response during the wound healing process.

Table 3

Nature of wound exudate in the comparison and main groups

Time (days)	Control group (n = 64)	Main group (n = 73)
2nd	Degenerative-inflammatory	Degenerative-inflammatory
3rd–4th	Inflammatory	Inflammatory-regenerative
5th–7th	Inflammatory-regenerative	Regenerative

At the next stage of the study, the immediate outcomes of onlay implantation of heavyweight and lightweight endoprostheses were analyzed in patients with postoperative ventral hernias. In both the main group and the comparison group, isolated cases of systemic complications were observed, with no statistically significant differences between the groups (Table 4). There were no fatal outcomes.

Table 4

Nature of systemic complications in the comparison groups

Type of complication	Main group (n=73)		Comparison group (n=64)		P
	abc.	%	abc.	%	
Coronary Heart Disease	1	1,4±1,4	2	3,1±2,2	>0,05
Iliofemoral thrombosis	2	2,7±1,9	1	1,6±1,6	>0,05
Tracheobronchitis	1	1,4±1,4	2	3,1±2,2	>0,05
Bronchopneumonia	1	1,4±1,4	-	-	
Acute urinary retention	1	1,4±1,4	-	-	
Total patients with complications	6	8,2±3,2	5	7,8±3,4	>0,05
Total patients without complications	67	91,8±3,2	59	92,2±3,4	>0,05

In two cases in the comparison group, tracheobronchitis was observed, which was treated with nebulizer inhalation sanitation of the bronchial tree, including the antibiotic Miramistin. In one case, the tracheobronchitis was nosocomial. In one case, the development of iliofemoral thrombosis was observed. Doppler ultrasound showed the thrombus to be fixed. Conservative treatment was conducted under the supervision of a phlebologist. In two cases, angina attacks were

observed against the background of ischemic heart disease (IHD).

In the main group, there was one case of angina attacks against the background of ischemic heart disease. In two cases, iliofemoral thrombosis was observed. Treatment was conducted according to standard protocols with the involvement of a phlebologist. In two cases, tracheobronchitis was observed, which was treated medically by inhalation of antiseptics and sanitation of the bronchial tree. In one case, bronchopneumonia was diagnosed in a patient with grade 4 obesity, which was considered nosocomial pneumonia, since the patient was on mechanical ventilation for two days. In one case, there was acute urinary retention against the background of benign prostatic hyperplasia. Urine was released by catheterization. It should be noted that the nature of systemic complications was not related to the use of heavy or light meshes.

Table 5 presents the structure of local complications in the postoperative period in patients with ventral hernias.

Table 5

Nature of local complications in patients with ventral hernias in the comparison groups

Type of complication	Main group (n=73)		Comparison group (n=64)		P
	abc.	%	abc.	%	
Seroma	3	4,2±2,1	8	12,7±4,1	>0,05
Infiltrate	5	6,9±2,8	2	3,3±2,1	>0,05
Suppuration of the postoperative wound	1	1,4±1,4	2	3,1±2,2	>0,05
Hematoma	1	1,4±1,4	1	1,6±1,6	>0,05
Wound edge necrosis	1	1,4±1,4	-	-	-
Lymphorrhea	-	-	1	1,6±1,6	-
Total patients with complications	7	9,6±3,5	11	17,2±4,8	>0,05
Total patients without complications	62	84,9±4,2	50	78,1±5,2	>0,05

Complications after alloplasty of hernia gates using lightweight and heavyweight polypropylene prostheses were observed in 11 (15.1%) and 14 (21.8%) patients, respectively. Wound complications after alloplasty included the development of seroma, infiltrate, postoperative wound suppuration, hematoma, edge necrosis of the skin-subcutaneous-fat flap, and lymphorrhea.

Seroma of the residual cavity was diagnosed in 3 patients (4.1%) in the group where the lightweight polypropylene mesh was used and in 8 patients (12.5%) in the group with the heavyweight polypropylene mesh. It is known that this complication is mainly observed after alloplasty for giant hernias using the onlay technique. To prevent seroma formation, a pre-prepared abdominal binder was applied on the operating table immediately after the surgery, which the patient wears during the early postoperative period to provide gentle compression of the tissues in the surgical area.

The postoperative hospital stay after alloplasty using Lightweight Polypropylene and Heavyweight Polypropylene mesh was 5.4± and 6.1±1.5 bed-days, respectively. Thus, the use of the Lightweight Polypropylene endoprosthesis was associated with a less pronounced and shorter exudative phase of the wound healing process, and the proliferative phase began earlier.

Analysis of superoxide dismutase (SOD) levels in serum and wound fluid in patients with postoperative ventral hernias (POVG) during the pre- and postoperative periods showed a similar trend in both the main (1st) and control (2nd) groups: in the early postoperative period, SOD levels in the serum decreased, but by the 7th day after surgery, they returned to baseline values.

This phenomenon is associated with the fact that, in the first days after surgery, the patients' antioxidant system (AOS) is under increased stress and actively consumes superoxide dismutase (SOD)—a key component of antioxidant defense. As physiological balance is restored by the end of the first postoperative week, AOS activity normalizes, leading to reduced consumption of SOD and, consequently, an increase in its serum levels. At the same time, in patients of the control (2nd) group, the recovery of the antioxidant system occurs more rapidly: the increase in SOD concentration is observed 1.3 times faster compared to the main (1st) group. This indicates that the alloplastic material used in the 2nd group induces a less pronounced oxidative stress.

The dynamics of changes in SOD levels in the blood serum largely reflected similar processes occurring in the wound exudate, as confirmed by the data (Fig. 4, Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. SOD levels in the blood serum of the examined patients before and after surgery at different time points (pg/mL)

The decrease in SOD levels observed on the first day after surgery is gradually replaced by an increase by the 7th day. By this time point, the concentration of SOD in patients of the 2nd group is 1.6 times higher compared to patients of the 1st group.

Fig. 5. SOD levels in the wound exudate of the examined patients before and after surgery at different time points (pg/mL)

Thus, when assessing SOD levels in patients with postoperative ventral hernias (POVG), both in complicated and uncomplicated postoperative courses, a similar trend of changes was observed. In patients of the 1st group, the lowest SOD levels were recorded on the 3rd day after surgery..

At the same time, in patients of the 2nd group, regardless of the nature of the early postoperative course, the SOD level remained relatively stable and showed a more pronounced recovery by the 7th day compared to the 1st group.

Conclusions

1. The study of clinical and laboratory parameters in the use of heavyweight and lightweight polypropylene mesh for alloplasty showed that the temperature response in the comparison group was significantly higher than in the main group. A moderate leukocytic response, with leukocyte counts ranging between 8,000 and 10,000 without a shift in the leukocyte formula, was recorded over a period of 6 days. Elevated leukocyte levels were observed on the 3rd to 4th postoperative days. In the comparison group, leukocytosis normalized by the 7th day, whereas in the main group, it resolved by the 6th day.

2. The use of the “Heavyweight Polypropylene” endoprosthesis in the onlay position for postoperative ventral hernias leads to a significant prolongation of the exudative phase of inflammation, with a peak wound discharge volume reaching up to 61.4 ± 4.2 mL on the 3rd day. In contrast, when using the “Lightweight Polypropylene” mesh, the peak discharge was limited to 25.6 ± 4.2 mL. By days 5–7, the wound process in the comparison group exhibited an inflammatory-regenerative nature, whereas in the main group it showed a predominantly regenerative character.

3. The study of postoperative complications in patients using “Lightweight Polypropylene” and “Heavyweight Polypropylene” endoprostheses showed a higher number of complications in the group with the “Heavyweight Polypropylene” mesh: postoperative wound seromas occurred in $12.5 \pm 4.2\%$ of cases ($p < 0.01$), compared to $4.1 \pm 2.3\%$ in the main group; wound suppuration was observed in $3.1 \pm 2.2\%$ and $1.4 \pm 1.4\%$, respectively; infiltrates were reported in $3.1 \pm 2.2\%$ and $6.8 \pm 3.0\%$ ($p > 0.05$), indicating better biocompatibility of the “Lightweight Polypropylene” prosthesis compared to the “Heavyweight Polypropylene.” Overall, postoperative wound complications occurred in $9.6 \pm 3.5\%$ of patients in the main group and $17.2 \pm 4.8\%$ in the comparison group.

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